

IDENTIFIED FACTORS AFFECTING THE INTEREST OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL PARENTS IN ATTENDING SCHOOL ACTIVITIES: BASIS FOR SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PLAN

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Abstract

The Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) in LFG Diamantina National High School has recorded low participation rate during homeroom meetings. This is evident in one PTA Meeting for a Grade 11 class wherein only 7 parents out of 21 attended despite the invitation given to each of them. Aside from general assembly some parents are not participative into school activities such as Brigada Eskwela where their involvement is highly needed. A total of ninety-three (93) parents participated in as respondents in this study: 41 from Grade 11 and 52 from Grade 12. This is the total number of SHS enrolment for this academic year. Mean and Pearson R is the main statistical used by the researcher. The researcher proved that IDENTIFIED FACTORS AFFECTING THE INTEREST OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL PARENTS IN ATTENDING SCHOOL ACTIVITIES: BASIS FOR SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PLAN strongly affects the Work-Related Factors, Family-Related Factors, Socio-Economic Factors, Child-Related Factors, School-Related Factors. The interest and support gathered by the respondents regarding interest of SHS parents has something to do with their high or low scores in the questionnaire test. The more interest or support of the parents they gathered, the higher the score and vice versa. With regards to the extension of the five factors it is strongly believed that in accomplishing satisfactory acceptance of the identified Factors Affecting the Interest of Senior High School Parents in Attending School Activities: Basis for School Improvement Plan the parents and teachers must have a smooth relationship for them to accomplish responsibility in the effective way. This study highly recommends that the parents' involvement should attend more school activities regarding on the improvement of their children.

Keywords: Interest, Senior High School, Parents, School Activities and Improvement Plan.

INTRODUCTION

In providing quality education to the learners, parents have pivotal role in molding the holistic development of their children. They are one of the stakeholders who support to uplift the spiritual, moral, social, and academic aspects of their children in order for them to become well-disciplined and productive individuals in the community. This is the reason the interest of the parents in the education of their children is highly recommended.

In connection to the study of Thornton entitled "Parental involvement stressed at education meeting" (August, 2017) Parents, educators, business people, clergy and concerned citizens gathered for discussion, and were asked to write down their groups'

ideas for dealing with the issues they identified. There were at least 75 people present through the course of the 90-minute-plus meeting; after the break-out discussions, they again came together to present their solutions.

Speaking for the parent group, some parents said they wanted to see parent-teacher-student organizations made mandatory in all schools, with the role of the organizations well defined and guidelines established for their operations, especially in how funds are distributed. Furthermore the parent group wanted improved transparency and communication for better relationships with parents. They were concerned as well with the student-teacher ratio and about whether all teachers are credentialed for what they do.

As an annual experience, the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) in LFG Diamantina National High School has recorded low participation rate during homeroom meetings. This is evident in one PTA Meeting for a Grade 11 class wherein only 7 parents out of 21 attended despite the invitation given to each of them. Aside from general assembly some parents are not participative into school activities such as Brigada Eskwela where their involvement is highly needed.

In the teaching-learning arena, the academic performance of the learners is a joint supervision both the teachers and the parents. Unfortunately some parents fail to get the progress report card of their children during recognition days which serve as an avenue for them to update and monitor their children's academic standing.

The abovementioned scenarios are just some of the root causes the researcher would like to know the factors affecting the Senior High School parents' interest in attending school-related activities in Luis-Fe Gomez (LFG) Diamantina National High School.

1. Research questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of interest of the parents of Senior High School students in attending school activities. Primarily, it identified the reason why the parents participate or do not participate in school activities that entails their presence. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What are the reasons of parents in attending or not attending school activities based on the following factors:
 - 1.1 Work-Related Factors
 - 1.2 Family-Related Factors
 - 1.3 Socio-Economic Factors
 - 1.4 Child-Related Factors
 - 1.5 School-Related Factors

2. Is there a significant interrelationship on the interest of parents in attending or not attending school activities when grouped according to the following factors:
 - 2.1 Work-Related Factors
 - 2.2 Family-Related Factors
 - 2.3 Socio-Economic Factors

2.4 Child-Related Factors

2.5 School-Related Factors

3. To what extent do parents attend school-related activities such as PTA Meetings, General Assemblies, Recognition Days, Commencement Exercises, among others?

4. What are the suggestions and recommendations of the parents as partners of the school administration in improving the school as an academic institution?

METHOD

Respondents

A total of ninety-three (93) parents participated in as respondents in this study: 41 from Grade 11 and 52 from Grade 12. This is the total number of SHS enrolment for this academic year.

Design

This study used the action research design which studies an on-going practice of a school, organization, community, or institution for the purpose of obtaining results that will bring improvement in the system. Through this study, the researcher was able to identify the possible reasons why parents of the SHS students attend or do not attend school activities. Besides, the researcher also analysed the extent of interest of the parents in attending school activities. Furthermore, this study served as an avenue for the parents to suggest and recommend ideas that may help the school administration to run the school in an operational and productive learning environment.

Materials

The instrument used in this study is a teacher-made questionnaire accurately constructed considering the highest possible reason parents attend or do not attend school activities.

In Part A, parent-respondents were asked to choose and tick identified reasons of their interest in attending school activities under such related factors namely: Work-related factors, Family-related factors, Socio-economic factors, Child-related factors, and School-related factors.

Each item on the questionnaire can either be a negative or positive statement, where the parent-respondents have the options to affirm or negate the identified reasons in attending or not attending school activities. A Likert-scale of 1-5 was used to indicate the degree by which the parent-respondent affirms or negates the given statement using the scheme: (5) – Always “Palaging dahilan”, (4) – Often “Madalas na dahilan”, (3) – Sometimes “Paminsan-minsang dahilan”, (2) – Seldom “Bhirang dahilan”, and (1) – Never “Hindi dahilan.”

In Part B, the parent-respondents provided the extent of their interest in attending school activities, their preferred day and time of meetings, and their suggestions and recommendations for the smooth operation of the school.

Procedure

The researcher constructed the questionnaire seeking some help from fellow SHS teachers and selected students, and sought the permission of the Officer-In-Charge, Joel R. Maltu, to conduct the study.

Gathered data were encoded using statistical software (SPSS). Using the same software, data were statistically treated. Mean distribution was computed for the reasons of parents in attending or not attending school activities. Frequencies and percentages was computed for the extent of interest of the parent-respondents in attending school activities and Pearson R for the interrelationships of the factors used in the research. Mixed method is used in the research both Qualitative and Quantitative analysis was used on the suggestions and recommendations of parents in the school operation.

Statistical Tool Used

The following Likert Scale was used to analyse the data gathered:

SCALE	INTERVAL	DESCRIPTION
5	4.21 – 5.00	Always "Palaging dahilan"
4	3.41 – 4.20	Often "Madalas na dahilan"
3	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes "Paminsan-minsang dahilan"
2	1.81 – 2.60	Seldom "Bhirang dahilan"
1	1.00 – 1.80	Never "Hindi dahilan"

RESULTS

For Work-Related Factors

Mayroon akong ibang business na pinagkakaabalahan kaya hindi ako nakadadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan. "I manage my own business that's why I don't attend school activities. Hindi ako pinapayagan ng aking boss sapagkat may deadline ang aking trabahong inihahabol." "My boss doesn't allow me to attend school activities because I have to meet deadlines on my work." Inuuna ko ang aking pagdalo sa mga pulong/piging/gawain para sa aking mga anak sapagkat mas mahalaga ito kaysa sa aking trabaho. "I attend first to the meetings or activities intended for my children because I know that these are more important than my job." Nakatuon ako sa aking trabaho sapagkat ito lang ang ikinabubuhay ng aming pamilya "I focus much on my job because this is the only means of living for my family." Isinasantabi ko ang aking trabaho para lang makadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan para sa aking mga anak. "I set aside my job just for me to attend school-related activities for my children." In the questionnaire being float the grand weighted mean is 2.60 and statistically interpreted as **seldom**.

For Family-Related Factors

Masaya kong tinatanggap ang gawaing nakatutulong sa aking mga anak dahil motibasyon nila ito para mapataas ang kanilang mga grado. "I am happy to accept responsibilities for the benefit of my children because this is their motivation to make their grades better." Nagiging makabuluhan ang aking aktibong paglahok sa mga gawaing pampaaralan dahil para ito sa ikabubuti ng pag-aaral ng aking mga anak. "Attending actively school-related activities becomes meaningful because this is for the better schooling of my children." Mayroon akong anak o matandang inaalagaan sa bahay kaya wala akong panahon na pumunta sa gawaing pampaaralan. "I take good care of a baby or an old man or woman at home that's why I don't have time to attend school activities."

Walang magbabantay sa bahay, sa tindahan, o sa mga alaga naming hayop. "No one will take charge of the house, in the store, or of our domestic animals."

Nadaragdagan ang aking pagsuporta sa aking mga anak sa pamamagitan ng pagsubaybay sa kanilang mga akademiko at ekstra -kurikular na gawain. "My moral support to my children becomes stronger by means of supervising their academic and extra-curricular activities.", Majority of the respondents positively believe that family-related factors with grand weighted mean of 3.00 and interpreted as **Sometimes**.

For Socio-Economic Factors

Wala akong sapat na pera para gamiting pamasaha sa pagdalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan at pambayad sa mga proyektong pangmagulang. "I don't have enough money for my fare in attending school activities and for paying school projects." Nahihiya akong dumalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan dahil sa pansariling dahilan tulad ng kapansanan, estado sa buhay, at iba pa. "I am shy in attending school activities due to personal reasons such as being a handicapped person, my low status in life, and others." Gustong-gusto kong makihalubilo at makipayanayam sa mga kapwa magulang at mga guro ng aking mga anak. "I really like to mingle and meet my fellow parents and the teachers of my children." Walang akong kasamang pumunta sa paaralan at dumalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan na nakaatang sa aming mga magulang. "I don't have any companion in attending school-related activities that are intended for us as parents." Ginagawa ko ang lahat ng paraan upang makadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan at mabayaran ang mga babayaran kahit ako ay makautang. "I do my best to attend school activities and pay for the school fees of my children even if I have to borrow money for it." Respondents agree that socio-economic factors poses positive and negative output with 2.20 grand weighted mean and interpreted as **seldom**.

For Child-Related Factors

Masaya akong dumadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan dahil gusto kong malaman mismo sa mga guro ang kalagayan ng aking anak sa kanyang pag-aaral. "I am glad in attending school-related activities because I want to know from the teachers the standing of my children in their studies." Gagawin ko ang lahat para sa aking anak kaya ipinapakita ko ang aking pagsuporta sa kanyang pag-aaral sa pamamagitan ng pagdalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan. "I do all my best for my children that's why I show to them my full support by attending school-related activities." Nahihiya akong pumunta

sa paaralan dahil sa mga nababalitaan kong pasaway ang aking anak sa kanilang klase. "I am shy in going to school because I heard that my son/daughter is often scolded for his/her misbehavior." Madalang o bihira na akong dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang sa paaralan dahil malaki na ang aking anak at kaya na niyang tumayo sa kaniyang sarili. "I seldom attend school activities for parents because my son/daughter is already old enough and he/she can already handle himself/herself." Masaya ang aking mga anak kapag nakikita nila ako sa paaralan na dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang. "My children are happy when they see me in school attending activities for parents.". It has a grand weighted mean of 3.06 and interpreted as **sometimes**.

For School-Related Factors

Gusto kong makita ang kalagayan ng paaralang pinapasukan ng aking mga anak kaya ako dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang. "I want to see the situation of the school of my children that's why I attend school activities for parents." Malayo ang paaralan ng aking anak kaya madalang o hindi ako pumupunta o dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang. "The school of my son/daughter is far from our home that's is why I seldom/never attend school-related activites." Panatag na ang aking loob sa pagpapatakbo ng mga guro sa paaralang pinapasukan ng aking anak kaya't hindi na ako dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang. "I am already at peace on the management of the school where my son/daughter studies that's why I no longer attend school activities." Masaya akong dumadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan dahil gusto kong maging saksi o bahagi ng pag-unlad ng paaralang pinapasukan ng aking anak. "I am happy in attending school activities because I want to witness and be part of the progress of the school of my son/daughter." Hindi ako napapadalhan ng liham paanyaya o naabisuhan ng mga namumuno sa paaralan kaya't hindi ako nakadadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang. "I don't receive any letter of invitation from the school management that's why I never attend school activities for parents." In the questionnaire being float the grand weighted mean is 2.45 and statistically interpreted as **seldom**.

Correlational Tests

Table 1. Interrelationship Among Respondents' Work, Family, Socio-Economic, Child Related and School Related Factors.

		Work	Family	Socio-Economic	Child	School
Work Related	Pearson Correlation	0.97	-.23	.026	.089	.044
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.445	.078	.77	.34
	N	93	93	93	93	93
Family Related	Pearson Correlation	-.220	1	.015	-.003	-.007
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.543		.237	.783	.344

	N	93	93	93	93	93
Socio-Economic Related	Pearson Correlation	.088	.078	1	-.009	-.009
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.056	.570		.765	.765
	N	93	93	93	93	93
Child-Related	Pearson Correlation	.076	-.785	-.049	1	-.994
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.589	.887	.882		.749
	N	93	93	93	93	93
School Related	Pearson Correlation	.891	-.078	-.059		1
	Sig. (2-tailed) N	.569	.882	.775	.895	.843
		93	93	93	93	93

Table shows that there is no significant relationship between parent attending school and not attending school in five factors conducted by the researcher. This means that the interest and support gathered by the respondents regarding interest of SHS parents has something to do with their high or low scores in the questionnaire test. The more interest or support of the parents they gathered, the higher the score and vice versa.

Using the Pearson coefficient of correlation, we discovered that the five variables are exhibit weak positive correlation.

Table 2. Descriptive Rating of Responses with Regards to the extent of parents attends school-related activities such as PTA Meetings, General Assemblies, Recognition Days, and Commencement Exercises. (Parents attending VS Parents Not Attending)

STATEMENT	PA		PNA		TOTAL		F-Val	SIG
	MEAN	DES	MEAN	DES	MEAN	DES		
Part I (Work, Family and Socio-Economic)								
Isinasantabi ko ang aking trabaho para lang makadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan para sa aking mga anak	3.18	VS	3.35	S	3.53	S	.590	0.446
Inuuna ko ang aking pagdalo sa mga pulong/piging/gawain para sa aking mga anak sapagkat mas mahalaga ito kaysa sa aking trabaho.	3.58	VS	3.17	S	3.38	S	.994	0.323
Nadaragdagan ang aking pagsuporta sa aking mga anak sa pamamagitan ng pagsubaybay sa kanilang mga akademiko at ekstra - kurikular na gawain.	3.65	VS	3.48	S	3.57	Vs	.179	0.674

Ginagawa ko ang lahat ng paraan upang makadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan at mabayaran ang mga babayaran kahit ako ay makautang.	4.00	VS	3.62	Vs	3.82	Vs	1.17	0.284
Part II. (Child and School Related Factors)								
Masaya Ang Aking Mga Anak Kapag Nakikita Nila Ako Sa Paaralan Na Dumadalo Sa Mga Gawaing Pangmagulang.	3.64	VS	3.40	S	3.52	VS	4.75	0.411
Gagawin Ko Ang Lahat Para Sa Aking Anak Kaya Ipinapakita Ko Ang Aking Pagsuporta Sa Kanyang Pag-Aaral Sa Pamamagitan Ng Pagdalo Sa Mga Gawaing Pampaaralan.	3.77	VS	3.45	S	3.62	VS	.880	0.317
Gusto kong makita ang kalagayan ng paaralang pinapasukan ng aking mga anak kaya ako dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang.	3.77	VS	3.52	Vs	3.65	Vs	1.01	0.453
Masaya akong dumadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan dahil gusto kong maging saksi o bahagi ng pag-unlad ng paaralang pinapasukan ng aking anak.	3.77	VS	3.52	VS	3.65	Vs	.570	0.453
Panatag na ang aking loob sa pagpapatakbo ng mga guro sa paaralang pinapasukan ng aking anak kaya't hindi na ako dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang.	3.32	S	2.90	S	3.12	S	1.10	0.289

Legend: Vs -Very satisfactory *- Significant S- Satisfactory

S- Satisfactory

Des- Descriptive

With regards to the work and family responses of parents' interest and support to their children as satisfactory shown by the overall means of 2.40. This proved that the extent of the two factors strongly task oriented.

With regards to the socio related factors is satisfactory shown by the overall mean of 2.20. This proved that the extent of the one factors strongly budget oriented.

With regards to the extent of child and school related factors it is satisfactory with 3.02 mean. However the two groups of respondents differ significantly in their responses with regards to the statement per category in the research questionnaire conducted by the researcher.

Table 3. The suggestions and recommendations of the parents as partners of the school administration in improving the school as an academic institution.

Generally after doing screenshots, note taking and focal interview to validate all the data gathered, it was found out that most of the parents are willing to sacrifice time and effort to attend school meetings and programs. This study highly recommends that the parents' involvement should attend more school activities regarding on the improvement of their children. Since Senior High School curriculum is new in Philippine Educational system the presence of the parents is well needed.

RESULTS

The researcher found out that Child-Related factors has the highest and among the five 1. Masaya akong dumadalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan dahil gusto kong malaman mismo sa mga guro ang kalagayan ng aking anak sa kanyang pag-aaral. "I am glad in attending school-related activities because I want to know from the teachers the standing of my children in their studies." 2. Gagawin ko ang lahat para sa aking anak kaya ipinapakita ko ang aking pagsuporta sa kanyang pag-aaral sa pamamagitan ng pagdalo sa mga gawaing pampaaralan. "I do all my best for my children that's why I show to them my full support by attending school-related activities." 3. Nahihiya akong pumunta sa paaralan dahil sa mga nababalitaan kong pasaway ang aking anak sa kanilang klase. "I am shy in going to school because I heard that my son/daughter is often scolded for his/her misbehavior." 4. Madalang o bihira na akong dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang sa paaralan dahil malaki na ang aking anak at kaya na niyang tumayo sa kaniyang sarili. "I seldom attend school activities for parents because my son/daughter is already old enough and he/she can already handle himself/herself." 5. Masaya ang aking mga anak kapag nakikita nila ako sa paaralan na dumadalo sa mga gawaing pangmagulang. "My children are happy when they see me in school attending activities for parents." It has a grand weighted mean of 3.06 and interpreted as sometimes. This support the study of Thorton (2017) that parental involvement must tense unity and love. There is no significant relationship between parent attending school and not attending school in five factors conducted by the researcher. This means that the interest and support gathered by the respondents regarding interest of SHS parents has something to do with their high or low scores in the questionnaire test. The more interest or support of the parents they gathered, the higher the score and vice versa. With regards to the work and family responses of parents' interest and support to their children as satisfactory shown by the overall means of 2.40. This proved that the extent of the two factors strongly task oriented. With regards to the socio related factors is satisfactory shown by the overall mean of 2.20. This proved that the extent of the one factors strongly budget oriented. With regards to the extent of child and school related factors it is satisfactory with 3.02 mean. However the two groups of respondents differ significantly in their responses with regards to the statement per category in the research questionnaire conducted by the researcher. This study highly recommends that the parents involvement should attend more school

activities regarding on the improvement of their children. Since Senior High School curriculum is new in Philippine Educational system the presence of the parents is well needed.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions of the study are that getting involved in the study affects the following:

- 1.1 Work-Related Factors- Positive Putative
- 2.2 Family-Related Factors - Positive Putative
- 2.3 Socio-Economic Factors - Positive Putative
- 2.4 Child-Related Factors - Positive Putative
- 2.5 School-Related Factors - Positive Putative

The interest and support gathered by the respondents regarding interest of SHS parents has something to do with their high or low scores in the questionnaire test. The more interest or support of the parents they gathered, the higher the score and vice versa. With regards to the extension of the five factors it is strongly believed that in accomplishing satisfactory acceptance of the identified Factors Affecting the Interest of Senior High School Parents in Attending School Activities: Basis for School Improvement Plan the parents and teachers must have a smooth relationship for them to accomplish responsibility in the effective way. This study highly recommends that the parents' involvement should attend more school activities regarding on the improvement of their children.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the research, the researcher is recommending for a deeper study on the following aspects:

1. Instill to have a Identified Factors Affecting the Interest of Senior High School parents in attending school activities in Division of Isabela;
2. Augment the result of the research to broadcast and share in other school in the Philippines; and
3. Treasure more basis improvement plan of the research result.

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